

PECULIARITIES OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN MODERN LIFE: ROLE, COMPONENTS, FUNCTION

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Annotation: This article highlights the characteristics of civil society today, its importance and main tasks. In addition to this, the main components and their importance in creating a civil society were given in article.

Key words: *spontaneity, activeness, legitimacy, ideological cornerstone, status-based, operational, mental, peace building, association, ethics, solidarity.*

Civil society is characterized by participation and doing. Central features of activity are spontaneity and activeness, autonomy and voluntariness. In civil society, laymanship and professionalism work side by side for the common goal. The essence of civil society is, thus, different from the two other main sectors of society, public and private. The public sector is characterized by the concepts of power, authority, legitimacy and democracy, whereas concepts typical of the private sector are markets, competition, profits, customership and consumerism. In civil society, activities are provided and services produced for members and customers in a non-profit making ethos. One ideological cornerstone of civil society is the charitable nature of its activities. The actors of civil society decide for themselves what kind of activities they engage in, although the financiers have begun to participate in the defining process more in the last decades. Project and

targeted funding have become more popular, and outsourcing services have increased.

Also non-formal adult education has been moderately regulated. In the last years, however, there has been a change in this practice. Project specific grants have increased, and the authorities have more control over the sphere of non-formal adult education[1]. Despite all this, autonomy remains as an essential characteristic of civil society. Another special feature of civil society is in the combination of laypersons and professionals. The peer support of those with similar life experiences forms an important part of the activities in organizations. The know-how of the members and volunteers is at use alongside the know-how of paid professionals. The soft and hard knowledge, the empirical and professional knowledge complement one another. Laypersons and professionals, voluntariness and paid work coexist in civil society. Civil society operates in a communal context. The activity can take place in status-based, operational, or mental (symbolic) communities[2]. The erosion of the traditional communality which was based on qualities such as status and descent, has not served to diminish the communal essence of civil society, because new kind of symbolic communality has emerged alongside the status-based communality.

Most of the activities of civil society take place locally and at grass roots. In civil society, people are at the same time actors and objects of the action. The members use decision-making power in defining the domain of civil society. Civil society is not stamped by customership or consumerism. Participation offers the opportunity and ability to have an influence. Ethics and solidarity are an important aspect of civil society, although the goodness of civil society should not be overemphasized. Like in any human activity, problems exist in civil society, too. Nevertheless, the starting point is the equality between individuals and the goal is the public good. The spontaneity and activeness of citizens stem first and foremost from the willingness to participate and act. People are motivated by an

interest in some subject matter. The willingness to participate, to take part and to obtain experiences brings substance to people's lives. Spontaneous activity acts as a good counterbalance to work and brings variety to one's life. Through participation a person can make new friends and break the circle of loneliness[3]. The desire to learn but also to help others encourages many people to be active and participate in the activities of civil society.

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Though civil society peace building efforts in developing countries have been instrumental in influencing positive change, their potential remains greatly undocumented and inadequately tapped in developing countries. The continued existence of conflicts, corruption, bad governance, poverty, and all the injustices that cause these vices in developing countries call for more civil society engagement with the local, national and international actors in establishing just relationships. Self-awareness of civil society actors in terms of the existing

opportunities for change is instrumental in building more solid and strategic alliances for a positive change. Though some of the opportunities discussed here may be used to undermine peace building efforts, this essay explores and demonstrates how these opportunities enhance the civil society organizations' peacebuilding functions.

Sum up, it should be noted that the meaning and implications of the concept of civil society have been widely debated. As an [analytical](#) framework for interpreting the social world, the idea that civil society should be understood as, by definition, separated from and opposed to the operations of the [state](#) and official public institutions has various disadvantages, not the least of which is that it [inhibits](#) appreciation of the complex interrelationships between state and society. Equally, the notion that the hugely [diverse](#) group life of Western capitalist societies promotes social values that are separable from, and possibly opposed to, the [market](#) is hard to defend[5]. The forms of combination and association that typify civil societies in the West are typically affected and shaped by the ideas, traditions, and values that also obtain in the economic sphere.

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